

A Walsh-based Arbitrary Waveform Generator for 5G Applications in 28nm FD-SOI CMOS Technology

Pierre Ferrer, François Rivet, Hervé Lapuyade, Yann Deval

University of Bordeaux, CNRS, Bordeaux INP, IMS, UMR 5218, F-33400 Talence, France

Abstract—This paper presents a novel Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG) based on Walsh’s theory for wideband radio frequency (RF) conversion. The architecture is dedicated to 5G-FR1 applications (sub-6GHz) to perform high bandwidth conversion while achieving high energy efficiency. A high-level simulation study is performed as well as transistor-level simulation including post-layout and Monte-Carlo analysis. A circuit is designed in 28nm FD-SOI CMOS technology from STMicroelectronics. It is composed of a Walsh sequences generator weighted by Walsh coefficients thanks to modified Digital-to-Analog Converters (DACs). It embeds an internal memory to feed the data to be converted for measurement purposes. The sum of the weighted Walsh sequences generates RF signals made of aggregated channels over a frequency range between 600 MHz and 4 GHz. The power consumption is 44 mW depicting an energy per bit of 0.34 pJ/bit, the lowest of the state of the art to the authors’ knowledge.

Index Terms—5G, broadband, carrier aggregation, Hadamard, sub-6GHz, Walsh Transform, Wideband.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 5G sub-6GHz standard (5G-FR1) uses spectrum over a wide band between 600 MHz and 5 GHz. It aggregates carriers using high-order modulations such as 64-QAM. Digital-to-Analog Conversion (DAC) architectures need to be revisited to generate direct RF signals. Current radiofrequency (RF) architectures are limited by their analog Front End which can only operate at specific frequencies, reducing the Carrier Component bandwidth to hundreds of MHz [1]. Wideband converters are generally obtained by using dedicated filters for each RF band as well as programmable Phase-Locked Loops which generate a variable Local Oscillator for RF mixers, increasing die area and power consumption while reducing spectral purity [2].

Time interleaving (TI) introduced in [3]–[5] is a technique used in converters to increase the data rate, where DACs are used in parallel, each one of them having an allocated time slot, and multiplexers merging each DAC value. This technique allows high data rate conversion, but is greatly sensitive to mismatches between converters, while also having poor energy efficiency.

Frequency Interleaving (FI) is a similar technique that allocates a frequency slot to each DAC reducing the bandwidth that needs to be processed per DAC, improving overall spectral purity. FI allows the generation of wideband signals, enabling carrier aggregation on all FR1 bands simultaneously. Most FI

architectures use narrow bandpass filters to split the signal spectrum [6].

This work proposes to directly use frequency domain data instead of the time domain to avoid any analog apparatus such as filters or mixers to perform carrier aggregation over wide bands. The Walsh Transform (WT) is similar to the Fourier Transform (FT) and performs conversion from the time domain to the frequency domain by using square sequences to build any signal rather than continuous waves (CW), which makes it more suitable for monolithic integration. This paper presents the design of an Arbitrary Waveform Generator (AWG) in 28 nm FDSOI CMOS technology from STMicroelectronics using the WT as initiated in [7] and demonstrated in [8] at MHz frequencies. This study aims to develop a large bandwidth architecture for 5G-FR1 frequency bands, aiming for sub-pJ/bit energy efficiency, and capable of simultaneously generating multiple modulated carriers across the entire band.

The WT is comprehensively explained in Section II. Subsequently, the proposed architecture is described in Section III. The simulation results are presented in Section IV. Finally, Section V concludes the paper and provides a comparison with the state-of-the-art.

II. THE WALSH TRANSFORM

The WT is a frequency transform with properties similar to the FT. It uses a basis of orthogonal square waves called Walsh sequences to generate arbitrary signals as depicted in Fig. 1. They are weighted by Walsh coefficients and summed to generate the signal. Eq. 1 shows the WT [9] with $x(t)$ the original signal, $Wal(n, t)$ the n^{th} Walsh sequence, C_n the n^{th} Walsh coefficient, M the number of Walsh coefficients and T the Walsh period.

$$x(t) = c_0 Wal(0, t) + \sum_{n=1}^M c_n Wal(n, t) \quad (1)$$
$$c_n = \frac{1}{T} \int_{t=0}^T x(t) Wal(n, t) dt$$

The Walsh sequences are described as follows:

$$Wal(n, t) = \Pi_i Rad(i, t)^{g_i} \quad (2)$$
$$Rad(i, t) = sgn(\sin(2^i \pi t))$$

where $Rad(i, t)$ is the Rademacher function. g_i is the gray coding of the Walsh sequence. Fig. 2 exhibits the first 8 Walsh sequences.

Fig. 1. Walsh conversion principle - A sum of weighted Walsh sequences by Walsh coefficient carries out a sinewave

Fig. 2. First 8 Walsh sequences

The Walsh coefficients are processed by the Walsh matrix $H_w(n)$ and the original signal as described in Eq. 3. The Walsh matrix is built by a permutation of the rows of the Hadamard matrix $H_h(k)$ according to the number of sign changes per row [10].

$$C_x(n) = \frac{1}{N} H_w(n) X(n) \quad (3)$$

$$H_h(k) = \begin{bmatrix} H_h(k-1) & H_h(k-1) \\ H_h(k-1) & -H_h(k-1) \end{bmatrix}$$

Main WT parameters are defined as follows:

- F_{Walsh} corresponds to the maximal Walsh sequence frequency. It determines the maximum frequency of the reconstructed signal $F_{max} = \frac{F_{Walsh}}{2}$.
- The Walsh order $walsh_order$ defines the number of Walsh sequences and coefficients M per period of Walsh

coefficients refreshment $M = 2^{walsh_order}$.

- $F_{refresh} = \frac{F_{Walsh}}{2^{walsh_order-1}}$ represents the frequency of Walsh coefficients refreshment.

$F_{Walsh} = 8$ GHz is chosen to cover the 0 – 4 GHz band as a demonstration and for ease of understanding as 8 GHz is a multiple of a power of 2. A $walsh_order$ of 6 leads to $F_{refresh} = 250$ MHz. A high $walsh_order$ reduces $F_{refresh}$ but increases the number of sequences. $F_{refresh}$ is optimum to refresh Walsh coefficients by DAC while maintaining a limited number of sequences, here 64.

The architecture of a Proof-of-Concept (PoC) circuit is presented in Fig. 3. It is composed of :

- a Walsh sequences generator with a frequency divider and a Walsh function generator,
- a Walsh coefficients generator with a Serial Peripheral Interface (SPI) to interface Walsh coefficients processed from an external device with embedded memory,
- a DAC-based sequences and coefficients combiner to carry out the RF signal.

III. WALSH-BASED ARBITRARY WAVEFORM GENERATOR

A. Walsh sequences generator

They are 2 kinds of Walsh sequences:

- The primary sequences are square signals with a duty cycle of 50%. They are generated by the division of F_{Walsh} with D flip-flops wired as frequency dividers. The architecture detailed in Fig. 4 uses 6 primary sequences with frequencies between 250 MHz and 8 GHz (W(1,t), W(3,t), W(7,t), W(15,t), W(31,t), W(63,t)).

Fig. 3. Architecture of the Walsh-based AWG

- The secondary sequences are generated by combining the primary sequences and the secondary sequences of the previous Walsh orders with logic gates. D flip-flops synchronize all the sequences from one to another. The last stage of synchronization of the sequences uses buffers because the last 32 sequences are too close in frequency to the clock signal to be synchronized with D flip-flops. The synchronization buffers are sized to compensate for the delay between the first 32 sequences and the last 32 sequences. Moreover, the back-gates of the transistors of buffers are used to adjust delays to compensate for the process variations (PVT) as shown in Fig. 5.

The layout is designed to ensure balanced propagation times between each stage by keeping similar connection distances between blocks.

B. Walsh coefficients generator

The Walsh coefficients are quantified on 8 bits including one signed bit and are refreshed at $F_{refresh} = 250$ MHz. The Walsh coefficients are calculated with MatLab and stored in an embedded memory accessible with an SPI. The memory has a size of 1.28 Mbits to be able to generate modulated signals respecting the 5G-FR1 standard with a duration of 10 ms.

C. DAC-based sequences and coefficients combiner

The weighting of the 64 sequences is performed by modified DACs based on current-summed differential pairs. The DAC output value is controlled by the commutation of its current sources and not by the differential pair transistor. The modified DACs detailed in Fig. 6 have a dynamic range of 7 bits. The 8th bit monitors the sequence inversion for signing. The weighting of the differential pairs is hybrid: the 3 Least Significant Bits (LSB) use a binary coding and the 4 Most Significant Bits (MSB) use a thermometer coding. This trade-off allows ensuring a good accuracy of the DAC while having a reduced footprint as detailed in [11]. The circuit is composed of 64 DACs, composed of 127 current unit pairs. The unit

current of each pair was chosen to ensure a measurable output power while limiting the total power consumption of the circuit. The current of a current unit pair is $I_0 = 10 \mu\text{A}$, giving a maximum total output current of 81.28 mA.

The current unit pair is detailed in Fig. 7. The M_{cs} transistors form a current mirror that copies the unitary current I_0 . The M_{sw} transistors form the differential pair which are commuted by the Walsh sequences. They are cascaded by two NMOS M_{casc} transistors to reduce the charge injection phenomenon. The M_{neu} transistors act as neutralizing capacitors. Their role is to reduce the charge injection brought by the C_{gd} capacitors of the M_{sw} transistors. Finally, the M_s transistors allow to turn off the pair, they are driven by the coefficients through the SW differential input. The M_{s2} transistors short-circuit the current mirror transistor, allowing a fast switching of the pair. The M_{s1} transistors open the circuit so that the current mirror does not consume power when it is turned off. The objective of enhancing this design is to preserve the square characteristics of the Walsh sequences by reducing the commutation delay. Additionally, it is crucial to ensure that each current pair exhibits minimal current glitches and leakage current. This is especially significant due to the massive parallelization of these current pairs (64 DACs), as any glitches or leaks would accumulate and result in significant errors. Therefore, minimizing glitches and leakage is necessary to maintain the integrity and accuracy of the overall system. In Fig. 8, a square signal at 8 GHz is depicted passing through a unary current pair, along with the corresponding switch-off signal for that pair. The commutation time for this operation is measured at 250 ps, accounting for approximately 6.5% of the coefficient period.

IV. SIMULATION RESULTS

A. Matlab Simulations

High-level simulations are performed in MatLab to validate the architecture with a test scenario composed of 3 aggregated 64-QAM modulated carriers, each having a bandwidth of 20 MHz. Those carriers follow the NR5G standard test model E-TM3.1 from [12]. Fig. 9 and 10 show a carrier at 700 MHz and two neighbor carriers at 3.51 GHz and 3.53 GHz. We evaluate a Spurious Free Dynamic Range (SFDR) of 45.85 dB, an Adjacent Channel Leakage Ratio (ACLR) of 51.04 dBc, and an Error Vector Magnitude (EVM) of 2.06% which results in a high-quality eye diagram exhibited in Fig. 11.

The impact of the delay between the first 32 sequences and the last 32 sequences is simulated in Fig. 12 to size the synchronization buffer detailed in Fig. 4. The 5G-FR1 EVM standard (EVM < 9% for 64-QAM) is met as long as the delay between the first 32 sequences and the last 32 sequences is lower than 12 ps. Monte Carlo simulations have demonstrated that PVT can shift the buffers by up to 4 ps. This is mitigated with back-gate voltage tuning thanks to the FD-SOI technology. The back-gate control can compensate for PVT delay shift up to 7 ps.

Fig. 4. Walsh sequences generator architecture

Fig. 5. Buffer delay variation with different back-gate voltage control

Fig. 7. DAC current unit pair

Fig. 6. 7-bit DAC

The jitter effect on the Walsh sequences is shown in Fig. 13, it is simulated by a normal distribution with a mean value of 0 and a standard deviation as a percentage of the maximum frequency (8 GHz). The 5G-FR1 EVM standard is met if the jitter standard deviation is lower than 12.5 ps (10% of F_{walsh}). Each stage is synchronized with D-latches to reduce sequence mismatches.

Fig. 8. Unary current source switch off transition

Fig. 9. Time domain multi-carrier 64-QAM signal (MatLab)

Fig. 10. Frequency domain multi-carrier 64-QAM signal (MatLab)

Fig. 11. Eye diagram and EVM constellation of QPSK, 16-QAM, 64-QAM aggregated carriers (MatLab)

64QAM : F0 = 3.52GHz, Fs = 64GHz, Fwalsh = 8GHz, Walsh_order = 6, Q = 8bits

Fig. 12. Impact on the EVM of the delay between the first 32 sequences and the last 32 sequences (MatLab)

Fig. 13. Impact on the EVM of the clock jitter (MatLab)

B. Post Layout Simulation

To evaluate the performance of the circuit depicted in Fig. 14, Post Layout Simulations (PLS) were conducted, the simulation shown in Fig. 15 involved the application of three continuous wave signals at frequencies of 0.7 GHz, 1.7 GHz, and 4 GHz, demonstrating the wideband capabilities of the architecture. The SFDR achieved was 15.14 dB, with an output power of -6.20 dBm, the post-layout measured SFDR exhibits a significant degradation compared to the MATLAB simulation, primarily attributable to mismatches, circuit limitations, and parasitic effects. The circuit exhibited a power consumption of 44 mW. The physical dimensions of the circuit include a pad-limited surface of 1.25 mm² and an active area of 0.282 mm². Based on Tab. I, the conversion efficiency of the circuit is 0.34 pJ/bit, which is the lowest reported value to the authors' knowledge.

The physical dimensions of the circuit include a pad-limited surface of 1.25 mm² and an active area of 0.282 mm². Based on Tab. I, the conversion efficiency of the circuit is 0.34 pJ/bit, which is the lowest reported value to the authors' knowledge.

V. CONCLUSION

A circuit using the Walsh Transform has been designed in 28 nm FD-SOI technology to generate 5G-FR1 signals. The architecture was validated by high-level and PLS simulations showing the ability of the WT to perform direct RF conversion and carrier aggregation over a wide bandwidth. The simulation

Fig. 14. Chip Layout

Fig. 15. Time domain and spectrum PLS of 3 CW (0.7 GHz, 1.7 GHz, 4 GHz)

TABLE I
STATE OF THE ART OF RF DACS

Paper	[3]	[4]	[5]	[13]	[14]	[15]	This Work
Cmos node (nm)	28	65	40	16	16	130	28
Maximum operating frequency (GHz)	4.4	4.1	13.34	5.2	3.9	20	4
Instantaneous bandwidth (GHz)	-	0.875	-	-	-	-	4
Consumption (mW)	360	380	103	530	350	1910	44
Output power @ max freq (dBm)	≈ 0	-8	≈ -22	-15.66	-	-18	-6.2
Quantization bits	13	16	16	12	16	10	8
Sample Rate (GS/s)	9	1.75	28	16	6	3.35	16
Efficiency (pJ/bit)	3.10	13.5	0.61	2.71	3.65	57.01	0.34

results highlight critical aspects mitigated by the design and the technology features and show preliminary performances with a bandwidth of 4 GHz, a power consumption of 44 mW, and a conversion efficiency of 0.34 pJ/bit.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The project HERMES has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 964246. Publication reflects only the author's view, the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

REFERENCES

- [1] B. Jann, G. Chance, A. G. Roy, A. Balakrishnan, Karandikar *et al.*, "21.5 A 5G Sub-6GHz Zero-IF and mm-Wave IF Transceiver with MIMO and Carrier Aggregation," *2019 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference - (ISSCC)*, pp. 352–354, 2019.
- [2] D. J. McLaurin, K. G. Gard, R. P. Schubert, M. J. Manglani, H. Zhu, D. Alldred, Z. Li, S. R. Bal, J. Fan, O. E. Gysel, C. M. Mayer, and T. Montalvo, "A highly reconfigurable 65nm CMOS RF-to-bits transceiver for full-band multicarrier TDD/FDD 2G/3G/4G/5G macro basestations," *2018 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference - (ISSCC)*, pp. 162–164, 2018.
- [3] J. Xiao, B. Chen, T. Y. Kim, N.-Y. Wang, X. Chen, T.-H. Chih, K. Raviprakash, H.-F. Chen, R. Gomez, and J. Y. Chang, "A 13-Bit 9GS/s RF DAC-based broadband transmitter in 28nm CMOS," *Symposium on VLSI Circuits*, pp. C262–C263, 2013.
- [4] E. Bechthum, G. Radulov, J. Briaire, G. Geelen, and A. van Roermund, "9.6 A 5.3GHz 16b 1.75GS/S wideband RF Mixing-DAC achieving IM<-82dBc up to 1.9GHz," *IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference - (ISSCC)*, pp. 1–3, 2015.
- [5] W.-C. Kim, D.-s. Jo, Y.-J. Roh, Y.-D. Kim, and S.-T. Ryu, "A 6b 28GS/s Four-channel Time-interleaved Current-Steering DAC with Background Clock Phase Calibration," *Symposium on VLSI Circuits*, pp. C138–C139, 2019.
- [6] G. Ding, C. Dehollain, M. Declercq, and K. Azadet, "Frequency-interleaving technique for high-speed A/D conversion," *Proceedings of the 2003 International Symposium on Circuits and Systems, 2003. ISCAS '03.*, vol. 1, pp. I–I, 2003.
- [7] N. Bouassida, F. Rivet, Y. Deval, D. Duperray, and A. Cathelin, "A concurrent transmitter in CMOS 28nm FDSOI technology based on Walsh sequences generator," *IEEE International New Circuits and Systems Conference (NEWCAS)*, pp. 1–4, 2016.
- [8] R. Quéhelle, F. Rivet, N. Deltimple, Y. Deval, and E. Kerhervé, "Demonstration of a Walsh-based Arbitrary Waveform Generator using Components Off-The-Shelf," *2021 28th IEEE International Conference on Electronics, Circuits, and Systems (ICECS)*, pp. 1–4, 2021.
- [9] J. L. Walsh, "A Closed Set of Normal Orthogonal Functions," *American Journal of Mathematics*, vol. 45, p. 5, 1923.
- [10] J. Johnson and M. Puschel, "In search of the optimal Walsh-Hadamard transform," *2000 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech, and Signal Processing. Proceedings (Cat. No.00CH37100)*, vol. 6, pp. 3347–3350 vol.6, 2000.
- [11] B. Razavi, "The Current-Steering DAC [A Circuit for All Seasons]," *IEEE Solid-State Circuits Magazine*, vol. 10, no. 1, pp. 11–15, 2018.
- [12] ETSI. (2017, 4) LTE, Evolved Universal Terrestrial Radio Access (E-UTRA), Base Station (BS) conformance testing. 3GPP TS 36.141 V14.3.0. [Online]. Available: https://www.etsi.org/deliver/etsi_ts/136100_136199/136141/14.03.00_60/ts_136141v140300p.pdf
- [13] D. Gruber, M. Clara *et al.*, "10.6 A 12b 16GS/s RF-Sampling Capacitive DAC for Multi-Band Soft-Radio Base-Station Applications with On-Chip Transmission-Line Matching Network in 16nm FinFET," *2021 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference (ISSCC)*, vol. 64, pp. 174–176, 2021.
- [14] C.-H. Lin, K. L. J. Wong *et al.*, "A 16b 6GS/S nyquist DAC with IMD lt;-90dBc up to 1.9GHz in 16nm CMOS," *2018 IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference - (ISSCC)*, pp. 360–362, 2018.

- [15] L. Duncan, B. Dupaix *et al.*, "A 10-bit DC-20-GHz Multiple-Return-to-Zero DAC With >48-dB SFDR," *IEEE International Solid-State Circuits Conference - (ISSCC)*, vol. 52, no. 12, pp. 3262–3275, 2017.